

Schrodinger Equation in Noninertial Frame as Constrained

Motion

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It seems that in the literature, when calculating the Schrodinger equation in a noninertial frame, say a rotating frame, a classical Hamiltonian is used. For example, the approach used for the classical Hamiltonian for a Lorentz force has often been applied to the rotating frame problem. The Schrodinger equation obtained using this Hamiltonian may then be rewritten in terms of a generator of the noninertial frame. For example, for a rotating frame: $(1/2m)(-idj + I e_{jlm} \omega_l r_m) (-idj + I e_{jlm} \omega_l r_m)W(r) - .5m\omega^2 r^2 + V(r)W(r) = EW(r)$ ((1)) becomes $-1/2m djdj W + V(r)W - \omega Lz W = EW$ ((2)). Equation ((2)) has the appearance of a constraint equation, with both EW and $-\omega Lz W$ being constraint terms. In the literature, the Schrodinger equation is sometimes obtained through a minimization of $W^* (-1/2m djdj) W + W^* V W = E W^* W$ by varying W^* and treating it as independent of W . In previous notes, however, we have argued that terms such as $-1/2m djdj W$ represent a conditional average using $P(p/r) = f(p) \exp(iprj)/W$, thus perhaps it is $f(p)$ that should be varied. In this note, we wish to examine the problem of the inertial frame as a constrained problem and to try to what physical ideas may be present.

Approach in the Literature

As described above, in the literature a classical Hamiltonian is often obtained and then converted into a quantum equation by changing p_j to $-idj$. In other cases, unitary operators are used. It seems, however, that a microscopic picture using a Fourier series is not usually utilized. In this note, we argue there may be a physical picture associated with the Fourier series approach based on conditional probabilities. In one dimension, the conditional probability is:

$$P(p/x) = f(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad \text{where } W(x) = \text{normalization constant} = \sum \text{over } p f(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

This suggests an unusual two channel probabilistic system with the channels linked in a periodic manner. We suggest there may be underlying physics associated with this picture, and that quantum mechanics is not the same as classical physics, even in a large n limit. Furthermore, because one utilizes all p values, it seems that if one places a quantum object in a potential, it will be 'knocked' from p level to another with different weights. At each point x , however, it seems that the unusual average of $p^2 P(p/x)$ added to the potential $V(x)$ gives E . It was argued that this represents a kind of resonance. In other words, if each $\exp(ipx)$ represents a different physical momentum state, then this picture should be retained when dealing with noninertial frames (which are related to constrained motion).

Constrained Motion

Next, consider the case of a noninertial frame, say a rotating or dilating frame etc. We argue that the noninertial frame represents a kind of constrained motion one believes is present in the system. For example, if a rotating frame is used, one is really

arguing that there is some average rotational energy in the system. This seems to represent a constraint. The question is how to incorporate such a constraint into the Schrodinger equation. In general, such a constraint may be thought of in two ways. The first involves a transformation of the velocity, for example for a rotating system one may write $v=v'+\omega r$ (where v' is the velocity in the rotating frame, and all three terms are vectors.) For a dilating system $v=v'+Crj$. In the Fourier series picture presented above, it seems that the potential $V(r)$ would knock particles from one state into another, including one ω (angular velocity) into another. On average, however, one might expect rotational motion related to ω . The question is how to create such an average. This leads to the second way of writing the constraint, namely the idea of a generator. With a generator, a specific number such as ω , the angular frequency, is not present in the generator itself, yet the overall type of motion (i.e. rotation) is captured. One way to obtain a generator is to consider equation ((1)) with $p_j=-id_j$ and to expand the squared term. Another approach is to find an operator which performs a translation, rotation, dilation etc. This operator is usually of the form of $\exp(i$ generator). Thus, for a rotation, one is led to an operator of the form of $L_z= xpy - y px$ which should 'pick up' the rotational tendency in the system. It is argued, however, that quantum particles are physically two channel systems governed by the complex probability $\exp(ip_jr_j)$. Thus, this physical behavior should persist even if there a physical rotation or translation in the system. In other words, the averaging of L_z must be done using the conditional probability $f(p)\exp(ip_jr_j)/W$. As a result, one may write the constraint as:

$$L_z W = \text{constant } W \text{ The constant may be called } \omega. \quad ((4))$$

Adding Constraints to the Schrodinger Equation

Equation ((4)) suggests a system may have a conditional average value for a generator of a noninertial frame, say a rotating frame. This, however, does not show how one should incorporate the constraint into the Schrodinger equation. In order to include a constraint in the Schrodinger equation, it seems it needs to be thought of as a variational equation i.e. one that may be varied until a proper solution is found. In this note, we use conditional probabilities so we cannot use the idea of varying W^*HW with respect to W^* as is usually done in the literature. In such a case, what should vary? We suggest that $f(p)$, the weight factor may be varied until one finds an equation which minimizes $-1/2m djdjW + VW - \omega L_z W - EW$ ((5)). Thus, there are two constraints in this equation, EW and $\omega L_z W$. One varies $f(p)$ until one finds one which makes ((5)) zero. In addition, one may look for the smallest E , which would represent a ground state. The Hamiltonian is a time evolution operator, so seeking an $f(p)$ which makes $-1/2m djdjW + VW - EW = 0$ indicates there is no overall change in time or a periodic change. In a sense, it seems by adding $-\omega L_z W$ (i.e. subtracting off the angular motion), one is attempting to find a solution which does not change in time (or changes in a periodic manner) with the constrained motion 'out of the picture'. Thus, rotational or other kinds of noninertial constrained motion have to be removed in order to see the resonance between kinetic energy and potential energy. The constrained motion is already in a kind of resonance state, one needs to next create a resonance between the remaining kinetic energy and the potential.

One may argue that the above consists of 'words', yet it seems there should be a microscopic picture of motion within a constrained system (say a rotating one etc). In

the literature, there are a number of papers which take the idea of different momentum states existing in potential seriously. For example, even a particle in a box with no potential except an infinite potential at the walls is seen to consist of all possible momentum states 'kicked up' by the potential. If such a picture holds there, it should also hold for a rotating system. Furthermore, if kinetic energy is averaged in a conditional manner using a complex conditional probability $f(p)\exp(ipx)/W$, such a probability should also apply to constrained motion. This probability is different from what one would expect classically, but if p is part of the constraint, as it is in a rotation or dilation, then the averaging process for p should not differ from the p^2 case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that instead of looking for a classical Hamiltonian which solves a problem in a noninertial frame, one might be able to find the generator of the noninertial frame and subtract it from the Schrodinger equation as a constraint in the form of constant Generator W

$$-1/2m \text{d}^2\text{W} + VW - EW - \text{constant Generator } W = 0.$$

This new equation, with the constrained motion removed may now be solved as a variational problem.

$f(p)$, the Fourier transform of W may be varied until the above equals zero suggesting that a resonance (with the constrained motion removed) has been obtained.